

**DEVELOPMENT OF ORAL SPEECH IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE
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This article aims to increase the interest of students of general Secondary School in the English language and to give them insight in simple ways as well as to make effective use of visual aids. Current research provides extensive explanation in terms of the development of speech perception and perceptual learning. One of the most basic tasks in teaching and educating students is to teach students the native language, as well as to teach foreign languages, from this point of view, to teach English. It is to get the student interested in the English language, to develop his speech in English, to teach speech attitude, manners. the main purpose of cultivation: is to develop the oral speech of students in the English language, the formation of the skills of conversational communication with the surrounding people. Speech integrative function includes many special functions: 1. To introduce students to classrooms and surroundings, to develop their speech, to enrich their vocabulary 2. Formation of the grammatic side of speech. 3. Nurturing the sound culture of speech. Working on the dictionary is also carried out by introducing visual weapons from the images in the classroom, as well as introducing them to the environment. In the process of acquaintance of readers with the objects on the sides, phenomena, plants, animal world, etc., we will tell their names, attributes, characteristics in English words. For example: the name of the items means: (things) mirror (Mirror) camp (comb), soup (soap), carteen (carpet), cupboard, (traumatic) bad (Kirov), tablecloth (tablecloth). Vegetables: (carrot(carrot), cabbage (cabbage), turnip (turnip), cucumber (cucumber), which means vegetables. Fruits: (fruits) apple (apples), pear (pears), cherry (Cherry), peach (peach), banana (banana), grape (grapes) domestic animals (pets) rooster (Rooster), hen (Chicken), horse (Horse), cow (Cow), dog (dog), cat (Cat), goat (goat). Verbs (representing action) washing (wash), cleaning (clean), doing iron (iron), cooking (brew) and others. Adjectives: words (adjectives) big (large), small (small), red (red), green (green), hot (hot), cold (cold), etc. are included in the dictionary of pupils in the process of acquaintance with the classrooms and environs of the students, as a result of which their dictionary is enriched, speech develops. In English lessons, it is very important to work with a dictionary, the teacher, with the help of a selective and diological speech, which will help the students to enter into a conversational

dialogue with their partner in English, will be able to enter into their speech. They not only teach students to understand the translation of words, but also become accustomed to actively practicing these words in speech. Dictionary is the building material of the language. Grammatics, however, determines the change of words in the sentence and their way of connecting. In addition, grammatics determines the construction model of the language (word-building, word-changing). The more early the reader mastered all the grammatical forms of the English language, the faster it develops both intellectually and in colloquial terms. If the grammatic side of speech is incorrectly formed in the reader, the development of the mind is delayed. The teacher must correct the grammatic mistakes in children's speech in each type of training and game. Not corrected in time, the grammatical error is strengthened in the child's speech, which also causes the appearance of grammatical errors in the speech of other children who listen to it. However, in specially organized games in child speech, it is necessary to timely eliminate thematikmatic errors that arise in the speech of the child by working on warning him or her of these negative aspects. In special organized games and classes, the child's attention is attracted only to the necessary grammatic forms. A word, a change in its form, a word combination or sentence, they remain the content of their mental activity. As a result of taking such classes consistently and consistently, children begin to understand how to speak, try to speak competently beautifully. Classes organized in the spirit of comfortable workmanship prevent the child from distracting attention, they carefully listen to the teacher's explanations, instructions, observe the speech of their comrades. They take a sample of speech in training and use it in their speech. Many students become the closest assistant of the teacher in correcting the mistakes of their fellow students. In carrying out special exercises, which are organized for the purpose of warning, correction of grammatical errors in children's speech, it is necessary to follow the following methodological instructions. Gram training on the formation of the right speech from the point of view has an instructive game character, in which visual materials or visualmasiz are conducted. For each initial class is selected instructional games, exercises corresponding to the program content. For example: for the first classes "English alphabet", "Numbers", "Domestic animals", "Family" and others. For the second class and higher classes, use Verbs, Jobs, Body, Seasons, Months and weeks, and so on. It is necessary to correct the mistakes in the child's speech with a friendly, kind attitude. Never repeat the mistake in the child's speech is naughty, it is permissible to repeat the words, educational games in which the

good is correct, the teacher during the lesson is obliged to monitor the child's speech and correct the grammatic mistakes during the yakiturly homogeneous games. In the reader's speech, it is necessary to correct thematikmatic mistakes in the course of the lesson in a sufficient tone of voice, making them more auditory to other students. In addition to teaching students how to speak correctly, it is also necessary to teach the sound culture of speech. Students will exchange some sounds because the English language has grown to the Latin alphabet. For example:” school “[sku:l] the word” school“,” book “[this:k] the word book,”bag ” [ba: g] bag. It is of great importance to teach colloquial speech (dialogue) in teaching knowledge and education to students. The formation of colloquial speech in a child is the ability to listen and understand the speech of others, to support colloquial speech, to answer and ask questions (ask questions). The degree of development of colloquial speech in a child depends on his vocabulary, on the possession of the grammatic side of the language. The appearance of school classrooms also occupies a special place. That is, the light should be enough, the tables, equipment should be suitable for the height of the pupils. There should be a constant sitting position of the students and the teacher, when the students are sitting at the table, the teacher should clearly see, the students should sit on the teacher, and the teacher-on the students. The air in the classroom should be constantly updated. In conclusion, I can say that the foundation of any strong-willed building is immortal. To some extent, this falsification also relates to the sphere of Education. Therefore, the more thorough the knowledge the student has in the class, the easier it will be to study in the upper classes. After all, the importance of kindergartens and schools, which serve as both a kindergarten and a primary school, can not be overemphasized for future students to adapt to school lessons, to be aware of the initial aspects of their cognitive skills. The teacher should pay special attention to students whose speech in the lesson is not well developed. Especially indecisive, one should approach the talkative pupils singly, not wanting to be polite, not being able to behave.

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